

The mitochondrial membrane protein FgLetm1 regulates mitochondrial integrity, production of endogenous reactive oxygen species and mycotoxin biosynthesis in *Fusarium graminearum*

Journal:	<i>Molecular Plant Pathology</i>
Manuscript ID	MPP-OA-17-227.R2
Manuscript Type:	Original Article
Date Submitted by the Author:	n/a
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Keywords:	<i>Fusarium graminearum</i> , Endogenous reactive oxygen species, FgLetm1, Mitochondrial integrity, Mycotoxin, Virulence

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3 1 **The mitochondrial membrane protein FgLetm1 regulates mitochondrial**
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5 2 **integrity, production of endogenous reactive oxygen species and**
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7 3 **mycotoxin biosynthesis in *Fusarium graminearum***

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34 15 **RUNNING TITLE:**

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36 16 Function of FgLetm1 in *Fusarium graminearum*

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38 17 **KEYWORDS:**

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40 18 *Fusarium graminearum*; Endogenous reactive oxygen species; FgLetm1;

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42 19 Mitochondrial integrity; Mycotoxin; Virulence.

43
44 20 Word count: 6997; Figure number: 8; Table number: 3.

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3 21 **SUMMARY**
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5 22 Deoxynivalenol (DON) is a mycotoxin produced in cereal crops infected with
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7 23 *Fusarium graminearum*. DON poses a serious threat to human and animal
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10 24 health and is a critical virulence factor. Various environmental factors including
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12 25 reactive oxygen species (ROS) have been shown to interfere with DON
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14 26 biosynthesis in this pathogen. The regulatory mechanisms of how ROS trigger
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16 27 DON production have been extensively investigated in *F. graminearum*.
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18 28 However, the role of the endogenous ROS generating system in DON
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21 29 biosynthesis is largely unknown. In this study, we genetically analyzed the
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23 30 function of Leucine zipper–EF-hand–containing trans-membrane 1(LETM1)
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25 31 super-family proteins and evaluated the role of the mitochondria-produced
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27 32 ROS in DON biosynthesis. Our results show that there are two Letm1
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29 33 orthologs, FgLetm1 and FgLetm2, in *F. graminearum*. FgLetm1 is localized to
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31 34 the mitochondria and is essential for mitochondrial integrity, whereas FgLetm2
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33 35 plays a minor role in maintaining mitochondrial integrity. The Δ FgLetm1 mutant
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35 36 demonstrated a vegetative growth defect, abnormal conidia and increased
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37 37 sensitivity to various stress agents. More importantly, the Δ FgLetm1 mutant
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39 40 showed significantly reduced levels of endogenous ROS, decreased DON
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41 41 biosynthesis and attenuated virulence *in planta*. To our knowledge, this is the
42
43 42 first report that mitochondrial integrity and endogenous ROS production by
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45 43 mitochondria are important for DON production and virulence in *Fusarium*
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47 44 species.
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43 INTRODUCTION

44 Deoxynivalenol (DON) is the most prevalent and economically important
45 mycotoxin associated with infested grains by *Fusarium* species (Desjardins,
46 2006). Among the *Fusarium* fungi, *Fusarium graminearum* is the main DON
47 producer that causes a devastating disease known as Fusarium Head Blight
48 (FHB) in cereal crops worldwide (Bennett & Klich, 2003, Desjardins, 2006,
49 Kimura *et al.*, 2007). The biosynthetic pathway of DON has been extensively
50 studied, and nearly all genes involved in DON biosynthesis (*TRI* genes) have
51 been identified (Desjardins *et al.*, 1993, Kimura *et al.*, 2001, Kimura *et al.*,
52 2007). Biosynthesis of secondary metabolites including mycotoxins is
53 influenced by various environmental factors. Previous investigations on the
54 regulation of DON biosynthesis in *F. graminearum* revealed the influence of
55 mycotoxin production by environmental or extra-cellular factors, such as
56 nitrogen and carbon sources (Jiao *et al.*, 2008, Miller & Greenhalgh, 1985, Oh
57 *et al.*, 2016), pH (Merhej *et al.*, 2011), magnesium (Pinson-Gadais *et al.*, 2009),
58 phenolic acids (Boutigny *et al.*, 2009), and amines (Gardiner *et al.*, 2009). Our
59 recent study showed that methylation of histone H3K4 also contributed to DON
60 production (Liu *et al.*, 2015). In addition to those factors, reactive oxygen
61 species (ROS) have been highlighted as a stimulator interfering with DON
62 production (Audenaert *et al.*, 2010, Ponts *et al.*, 2007, Ponts *et al.*, 2006,
63 Montibus *et al.*, 2013, Jiang *et al.*, 2015). Supplementation with hydrogen
64 peroxide (H₂O₂) or the fungicide prothioconazole to the liquid cultures of *F.*
65 *graminearum* were able to significantly increase the concentration of
66 intracellular ROS, which subsequently stimulated *TRI* gene expression and
67 induced DON production (Audenaert *et al.*, 2010, Ponts *et al.*, 2007, Ponts *et*

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3 68 *al.*, 2006). Relatively higher concentrations of H₂O₂ were observed in the
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5 69 infection cushions, as compared to runner hyphae during the infection process
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7 70 of *F. graminearum* (Mentages & Bormann, 2015). However, the mechanism to
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9 71 generate endogenous ROS, and the role of ROS the regulation of DON
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11 72 biosynthesis remain relatively unknown in *F. graminearum*.
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14 ROS are able to cause DNA damage, lipid peroxidation, and protein
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16 74 oxidation (Beckman & Ames, 1998). Alternatively, ROS have been suggested
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18 75 to be a secondary messenger that transduces signals to regulate cellular
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20 76 functions such as immunity, cell proliferation and ion transport in mammals and
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22 77 plants. In microbial eukaryotes, ROS have been shown to be involved in
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24 78 regulation of life-span (Osiewacz, 2002), host-pathogen interactions and other
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26 79 cellular functions (Missall *et al.*, 2004, Nowikovsky *et al.*, 2004). Mitochondria
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28 80 are the major source of endogenous ROS, and produce about 95% of the total
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30 81 of ROS during cellular oxidative metabolism (Liu, 1999). Meanwhile, several
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32 82 enzymatic and non-enzymatic systems are also involved in intracellular ROS
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34 83 production (Grissa *et al.*, 2010). The most important enzymatic
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36 84 ROS-generating system is the NADPH-dependent oxidase complex (Nox).
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38 85 The role of NADPH oxidases NoxA and NoxB and the regulator NoxR in ROS
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40 86 production have been investigated in *F. graminearum* (Wang *et al.*, 2014,
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42 87 Zhang *et al.*, 2016). However, the roles of mitochondria and the mitochondrial
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44 88 ROS-generating system in secondary metabolism and virulence of
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46 89 phytopathogenic fungi, including *F. graminearum*, have not been investigated.
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51 Leucine zipper–EF-hand–containing transmembrane 1(LETM1), an inner
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53 91 mitochondrial membrane protein, has been identified as a protein associated
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55 92 with Wolf-Hirschhorn syndrome (WHS), a complex multigenic human disease
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3 93 caused by the partial deletion of the distal short arm of chromosome 4 (Endele
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5 94 *et al.*, 1999, Zollino *et al.*, 2003). Letm1 is evolutionarily conserved from yeast
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7 95 to mammals. The biological functions of the Letm1 orthologs have been
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10 96 investigated in various organisms (Dimmer *et al.*, 2008, Hasegawa & van der
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12 97 Bliiek, 2007, Hashimi *et al.*, 2013, McQuibban *et al.*, 2010, Nowikovskiy *et al.*,
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14 98 2004, Zhang *et al.*, 2012). However, the function of the Letm1 super-family in
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16 99 filamentous fungi is still largely unknown. In this study, the Letm1 orthologs
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18 100 were selected as target proteins to investigate the biological function of ROS
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20 101 generated from mitochondria and mitochondrial integrity in DON biosynthesis,
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22 102 virulence and cell development. Our results showed that the deletion mutant
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24 103 Δ FgLetm1 had a vegetative growth defect and abnormal conidia. The mutant
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26 104 was also more sensitive to various stress agents. More importantly, Δ FgLetm1
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28 105 significantly reduced the levels of cellular ROS, decreased DON biosynthesis
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30 106 and attenuated virulence *in planta*.
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36 108 **RESULTS**

37 109 **Identification and sequence analysis of Letm1-like proteins in *Fusarium*** 38 39 ***graminearum*** 40 41 110 ***graminearum***

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43 111 A BLASTP search using *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* Letm1 family proteins,
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45 112 Mdm38 and Ylh47, as queries in the *F. graminearum* genome revealed only
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47 113 one putative Letm1 gene in this fungus, FGSG_09158 (designated as
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49 114 FgLetm1). The *FgLETM1* gene is predicted to encode a protein with 550
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51 115 amino acids, sharing 47% and 45% sequence identity with Mdm38 and Ylh47,
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53 116 respectively. Meanwhile, we retrieved other genes with the LETM1
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55 117 super-family domain in the *F. graminearum* genome, and found that the
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3 118 FGSG_10063 locus (designated as FgLetm2) also contained a LETM1
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5 119 super-family domain. However, FgLetm2 shares very low sequence identity
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7 120 with Mdm38 and Ylh47 (9.8% and 11.4%, respectively). Similar to *S.*
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9 121 *cerevisiae* Letm1 orthologs, FgLetm1 contains a noncanonical Letm1 protein
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11 122 structure with a Letm1 super-family domain, a transmembrane (TM) domain
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13 123 and a coiled-coil domain at the carboxyl terminus. The FgLetm2 protein
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15 124 harbors a truncated Letm1 super-family domain after the TM domain at the
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17 125 carboxyl terminus (Fig. 1a). Both FgLetm1 and FgLetm2 lack the EF-hand
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19 126 domain present in human Letm1 (NP_036450). This was consistent with a
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21 127 previous study, in which it was demonstrated that the EF-hand domain was
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23 128 absent in lower eukaryotes, fungi and plasmodium (Nowikovsky et al., 2004).

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27 129 To gain more insight into the Letm1 evolution in fungi, we retrieved all
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29 130 genes that encode proteins containing the Letm1 super-family domain from 32
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31 131 fungal genomes available in the NCBI Bioprojects and Broad Institute
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33 132 database. The results indicated that genes for the Letm1-like proteins are
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35 133 highly conserved in fungi, while the number of orthologs varies in different
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37 134 fungal species. Most fungal species (25 out 32) harbored two orthologs, albeit
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39 135 the representative fungi from *Taphrinomycotina*, *Pucciniomycotina* and
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41 136 *Chytridiomycota* contained only one Letm1-like protein. Moreover, three
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43 137 different genes encoding the Letm1-like proteins were retrieved from
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45 138 *Zygomycota* fungi *Rhizopus oryzae* and *Mucor circinelloides* (Fig. S1). A
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47 139 phylogenetic analysis of the putative Letm1-like proteins, which include *F.*
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49 140 *graminearum* and six filamentous phytopathogenic fungi, showed that the
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51 141 Letm1-like proteins are significantly divided into two groups (Fig. 1b). Proteins
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53 142 in group II had a truncated Letm1 super-family domain with a length of 58-75
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3 143 amino acids (Table S1). The domain characteristic and the phylogenetic tree
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5 144 indicated that FgLetm1 might have similar biological functions to the Letm1
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7 145 proteins Mdm38 and Yln47 in *S. cerevisiae*.

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10 146 In addition, our in-house RNA-seq data indicated that the transcriptional
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12 147 level of *FgLETM1* was higher than that of *FgLETM2*, by a range of 5- to 20-
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14 148 fold higher, in all four tested conditions including in the conidiation medium
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16 149 (CMC), hyphae grown in PDA, plant infection and deoxynivalenol (DON)
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18 150 biosynthesis induction medium (TBI) (Fig. 1c).

20 21 151 **Disruption of FgLetm1 and FgLetm2**

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23 152 To characterize the function of FgLetm1 and FgLetm2, we generated single
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25 153 and double deletion mutants, Δ FgLetm1, Δ FgLetm2 and $\Delta\Delta$ FgLetm1/2, using
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27 154 the homologous recombination strategy. The single or double deletion mutants
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29 155 were confirmed by Southern hybridization assays (Fig. S2). To confirm that the
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31 156 phenotypic abnormalities of the mutants were directly related to the deletion,
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33 157 we complemented the deletion mutants with the gene fused with *gfp* for the
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35 158 green fluorescent protein (GFP) at the carboxyl terminus under their native
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37 159 promoters, respectively, and generated the complemented strain Δ FgLetm1-C
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39 160 (Δ FgLetm1+P_{LETM1} FgLetm1-GFP) and Δ FgLetm2-C (Δ FgLetm2+P_{LETM2}
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41 161 FgLetm2-GFP) . The complemented strains were also confirmed by Southern
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43 162 blot assays and PCR amplification (Fig. S2).

44 45 46 47 163 **FgLetm1 regulates hyphal growth, conidiation and conidial germination**

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49 164 The Δ FgLetm1 mutant demonstrated radial and hyphal growth defects. The
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51 165 rate of radial growth of Δ FgLetm1 was reduced on both PDA (potato dextrose
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53 166 agar) and MM (minimal medium), in comparison with that of wild type PH-1,
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55 167 respectively. Moreover, the deletion mutant of Δ FgLetm1 exhibited a reduction
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3 168 in aerial hyphae formation on solid agar plates (Fig. 2 a).
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5 169 Δ FgLetm1 produced less conidia than that of the wild type PH-1 after 4
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7 170 days of incubation in CMC (Table 1). To further examine conidial morphology,
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9 171 calcofluor white staining assays were performed for individual mutants. The
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11 172 results were observed under the fluorescent microscope. As shown in Fig. S3
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13 173 and Table 1, the size of conidia produced by Δ FgLetm1 was shorter, in
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15 174 comparison with that of the wild type. Moreover, the conidia of Δ FgLetm1
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17 175 harbored fewer septa. Most of the conidia (65%) had only 3 septa in the
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19 176 Δ FgLetm1, while the majority of conidia produced by wild type had 5 septa (Fig.
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21 177 2b). Meanwhile, the abnormal conidia of Δ FgLetm1 showed slower
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23 178 germination than that of the wild type in the present of 2% sucrose (Fig. 2c).
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27 179 In contrast, the deletion mutant of Δ FgLetm2 did not show visible
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29 180 phenotypic differences in vegetative growth, conidia formation and germination,
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31 181 in comparison with that of the wild type. The $\Delta\Delta$ FgLetm1/2 double mutant
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33 182 demonstrated similar phenotypes as those in the Δ FgLetm1 single mutant.
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35 183 Phenotypic defects of Δ FgLetm1 were restored by the complementation in the
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37 184 complemented strain Δ FgLetm1-C (Fig. 2). Thus, our evidences confirmed that
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39 185 the defects in the mutants were linked to the loss of the *FgLETM1* gene. Taken
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41 186 together, the data presented here suggested that FgLetm1 is involved in the
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43 187 hyphal growth, conidiation and conidial germination, and that FgLetm2 plays
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45 188 a dispensable role in these biological processes under the tested conditions.
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49 189 **Deletion mutant of Δ FgLetm1 showed increased sensitivity towards**
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52 190 **osmotic stress, heat shock and fungicides**

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54 191 It has been reported that Mdm38 is involved in resistance to several biotic
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56 192 stresses in yeast (Frazier *et al.*, 2006, Sinha *et al.*, 2008, Dimmer *et al.*, 2002a).
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3 193 Therefore, we were interested in determining the susceptibility of the mutants
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5 194 in *F. graminearum* to various stresses, including osmotic stress, heat shock,
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7 195 and fungicide treatment. The susceptibility assays showed that the $\Delta FgLetm1$
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10 196 mutant had a significantly increased sensitivity to osmotic stresses generated
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12 197 by NaCl or KCl, whereas the $\Delta FgLetm2$ mutant displayed the same
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14 198 susceptibility to that of the wild type towards osmotic stresses (Figs. 3a, b).
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16 199 The heat tolerance of the mutants was examined at 15 °C, 25 °C and 32 °C. As
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18 200 shown in Fig. 3c, all strains displayed similar growth rate as that of the wild
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20 201 type at 15 °C. For growth at 32 °C, noticeably, the $\Delta FgLetm1$ mutant could not
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22 202 grow at 32 °C. The complemented strains had similar growth rate and colony
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24 203 morphology with the wild type PH-1. Therefore, our results indicated that
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26 204 $\Delta FgLetm1$ increased sensitivity to heat shock stress. To further confirm the
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28 205 increase of sensitivity to high temperatures in $\Delta FgLetm1$, we assayed the
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30 206 transcriptional levels of the *FgHSP30* (Fg01158), *FgHSP70* (Fg00838), and
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32 207 *FgGSY2*(Fg06822) genes, whose products are involved in the heat shock
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34 208 tolerance in *F. graminearum* (Hu et al., 2014). When cultures were shifted from
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36 209 25°C to 32°C for 1 h, the relative expression levels of *FgHSP70* and *FgHSP30*
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38 210 were 2.5- and 2-fold higher, respectively, in PH-1 compared to that of
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40 211 $\Delta FgLetm1$ (Fig. 3d). Therefore, the deletion mutant of $\Delta FgLetm1$ decreased
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42 212 the expression of the selected heat stress response genes in *F. graminearum*.
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47 The susceptibility of the mutants towards ions and fungicides were also
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49 214 examined. $\Delta FgLetm1$ displayed more sensitivity to iprodione, phenamacril,
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51 215 $FeSO_4$ and $CaCl_2$ than that of the wild type and complemented strains (Fig. 3e,
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53 216 f). In particular, the $\Delta FgLetm1$ mutant was hyper-sensitive to Fe^{2+} and could
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55 217 not grow on the MM amended with 10 mM Fe^{2+} . It implied that *FgLetm1* might
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3 218 regulate the ferrum homeostasis in this fungus. The double mutant
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5 219 $\Delta\Delta$ FgLetm1/2 showed similar phenotypes with that of Δ FgLetm1 in all tested
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7 220 conditions.

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10 221 **FgLetm1 is localized to the mitochondria and is critical for mitochondrial**
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12 222 **integrity**

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14 223 The complemented strains Δ FgLetm1-C and Δ FgLetm2-C with GFP-fusion
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16 224 proteins were rescued for the phenotypic defects seen in the mutants (Figs.
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18 225 2-3), indicating that the fusion proteins were functional. These strains were
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20 226 further used for observing the subcellular localization of FgLetm1 and FgLetm2.
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22 227 A filamentous network pattern of GFP signals was present in the vegetative
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24 228 mycelia of the Δ FgLetm1-C strain (Fig. 4a). Co-localization experiments were
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26 229 performed using dual-labeling with FgLetm1-GFP and mitochondrial indicator
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28 230 Mito-HcRed staining. As shown in Fig. 4a, the GFP and Mito-HcRed signals
29
30 231 clearly overlapped, suggesting that FgLetm1 was localized to the mitochondria.
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32 232 Using the same assay, we observed that FgLetm2-GFP was also
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34 233 co-localized with Mito-HcRed (Fig. 4a). Therefore, both FgLetm1 and FgLetm2
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36 234 were localized to the mitochondria.

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38 235 Since both FgLetm1 and FgLetm2 were shown to be mitochondria
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40 236 localized proteins, we were interested in testing whether the deletion mutants
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42 237 would show altered mitochondrial structures. First, the mitochondrial patterns
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44 238 were observed by Mito-HcRed staining. Mito-HcRed signal in the mycelia of
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46 239 PH-1 and the complemented strains dominantly showed the filamentous
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48 240 network shapes (Fig. 4b, video S1), while it displayed punctate patterns in the
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50 241 mycelia of the Δ FgLetm1 single and the double mutant (Fig. 4b, video S2).
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52 242 Interestingly, mitochondrial mobility was relatively slower in the Δ FgLetm1
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3 243 mutant than in the wild type (videos S1, S2). This implied that the
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5 244 mitochondrial morphology and function might be different in PH-1 and
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7 245 $\Delta FgLetm1$. Next, transmission electron microscope (TEM) experiment was
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9 246 applied to visualize the details of the mitochondrial structures. The TEM
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11 247 micrographs revealed that the deletion of the *FgLETM1* gene caused
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13 248 mitochondrial swelling, an increase in mitochondrial volume and a lack of
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15 249 tubular shaped cristae structures (Fig. 4c). The mitochondrial morphologies in
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17 250 the $\Delta FgLetm2$ cells showed similar shape and cristae structures in comparison
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19 251 with that in PH-1, while the volume was slightly increased. The abnormal
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21 252 mitochondrial morphologies of the double mutant were consistent with those of
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23 253 the $\Delta FgLetm1$ mutant (Figs. 4b, c). In yeast, Mdm38 is essential for the
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25 254 biosynthesis of the respiratory chain components (Frazier et al., 2006). To test
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27 255 whether *FgLetm1* has a similar function in *F. graminearum*, we selected
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29 256 cytochrome *b* (*Cyt b*) as the indicator protein of respiratory chain components,
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31 257 and detected the protein level of *Cytb* by western blotting. As shown in Fig. 4d,
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33 258 the abundance of the *Cyt b* protein was clearly decreased in $\Delta FgLetm1$ and
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35 259 the double mutant. Our findings thus strongly suggested that *FgLetm1* is a
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37 260 structural protein, which helps to maintain the mitochondrial structure and is
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39 261 essential for the biosynthesis or the stability of the components in the
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41 262 respiratory chain, whereas *FgLetm2* might play a minor role in these
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43 263 processes.

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49 264 **The deletion mutant of $\Delta FgLetm1$ decreased the production of**
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51 265 **endogenous ROS and reduced ATP biosynthesis**

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53 266 Mitochondria are an important source of ATP synthesis and ROS production in
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55 267 eukaryotic cells. Given that the deletion mutant of $\Delta FgLetm1$ resulted in
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3 268 mitochondrial dysfunction, we next compared the concentration of intracellular
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5 269 ROS and ATP biosynthesis in all above strains. The ROS content was
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7 270 qualitatively analyzed with H2DCFDA (2', 7'-dichlorodihydrofluorescein
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10 271 diacetate) staining in MM and TBI. As indicated in Fig. 5a, the mycelia of the
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12 272 wild type, $\Delta FgLetm2$ and complemented strains were all stained by the dye
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14 273 and cells showed green signals under fluorescent microscope. Interestingly,
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16 274 mycelia of the wild type, $\Delta FgLetm2$ and complemented strains were swelled
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18 275 and formed ovoid toxigenic cells, and displayed noticeably stronger green
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20 276 signals in TBI (Fig. 5a, bottom panel) than in MM (Fig. 5a, upper panel). These
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22 277 results suggested that ROS production were highly induced and ROS was
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24 278 accumulated in cells during DON biosynthesis. However, limited fluorescent
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26 279 signals were detected in $\Delta FgLetm1$ and the double mutant in both media (Fig.
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28 280 5a). Quantification data also confirmed that endogenous ROS was significantly
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30 281 reduced in $\Delta FgLetm1$ and $\Delta\Delta FgLetm1/2$ (Table 2). Intracellular ROS levels
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32 282 are usually balanced by the activities of catalases and superoxide dismutases.
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34 283 Therefore, we performed qRT-PCR to measure the transcripts of seven
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36 284 putative catalase and superoxide dismutase genes in the mycelia of the wild
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38 285 type and the $\Delta FgLetm1$ mutant after 3 days of incubation in TBI. As expected,
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40 286 the qRT-PCR results indicated that all selected genes, except for *FgZnSOD2*,
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42 287 showed very low transcriptional levels in $\Delta FgLetm1$ in response to limited
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44 288 intracellular ROS-mediated oxidative stress, in comparison with their
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46 289 expression levels in the wild type (Fig. 5b). To determine whether the reduction
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48 290 of intercellular ROS in $\Delta FgLetm1$ and the double mutant would lead to their
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50 291 higher tolerance towards extracellular ROS stress, we measured the sensitivity
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52 292 of all strains to oxidative stress on the MM supplemented with 10 mM H_2O_2 .
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3 293 Deletion mutant of $\Delta FgLetm1$ and the double mutant exhibited significantly
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5 294 increased tolerance to oxidative stress mediated by H_2O_2 compared to that of
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7 295 the wild type, $\Delta FgLetm2$ and complemented strains (Fig. 5c, d).
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10 296 We next measured ATP production in the deletion mutants. The
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12 297 quantification data indicated that the production of ATP in the $\Delta FgLetm1$ and
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14 298 the double mutant was decreased about 30%, compared with that of the wild
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16 299 type. The $\Delta FgLetm2$ mutant and the complemented strains produced ATP at a
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18 300 level similar to that of the wild type strain (Table 2). In mammals, LETM1
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20 301 knock-down led to mitochondrial malfunction and an induction of glycolysis in
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22 302 the cytoplasm to maintain their ATP supply in these cells (Dimmer et al., 2008,
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24 303 Hwang *et al.*, 2010). To investigate whether the dysfunctional mitochondria in
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26 304 $\Delta FgLetm1$ also increases glycolysis, we measured the concentration of
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28 305 ethanol, the byproduct of anaerobic respiration in fungi, in MM after 16 h of
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30 306 incubation. As expected, the ethanol concentration of the cell-free supernatant
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32 307 from the $\Delta FgLetm1$ mutant was significantly elevated compared to the wild
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34 308 type (Table 2), indicating that the *FgLETM1* deletion disrupted the respiration
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36 309 chain and up-regulated the glycolytic pathway in *F. graminearum*. Collectively,
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38 310 our data suggested that *FgLetm1* is critical for normal mitochondrial function in
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40 311 ATP generation and ROS production.
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45 312 **The $\Delta FgLetm1$ mutant is significantly attenuated in virulence**

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47 313 On wheat heads inoculated with PH-1, or $\Delta FgLetm2$, or the complemented
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49 314 strains, scab symptoms were first developed on the inoculated spikelets and
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51 315 rapidly spread to the whole wheat head after 15 days of inoculation. In contrast,
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53 316 the hyphal growth of $\Delta FgLetm1$ or the $\Delta\Delta FgLetm1/2$ double mutant failed to
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55 317 spread from the inoculated floret to the rachis, and subsequently caused scab
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3 318 symptoms only in the inoculated spikelet (Fig. 6a, upper panel). Moreover,
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5 319 almost all grains in infected wheat ears by wild-type PH-1, $\Delta FgLetm2$ and
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7 320 complemented strains were shriveled and bleached, while only the grain at the
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9 321 inoculated site was shrunken in the treatment of $\Delta FgLetm1$ and $\Delta\Delta FgLetm1/2$
10
11 322 (Fig. 6a, bottom panel). Since that $\Delta FgLetm1$ and $\Delta\Delta FgLetm1/2$ mutants grew
12
13 323 well on the wheat head tissue medium (WA) (Fig. S4), the attenuated virulence
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15 324 of $\Delta FgLetm1$ and $\Delta\Delta FgLetm1/2$ was not likely due to the growth defect. Next,
16
17 325 we investigated whether the deletion mutations affected the penetration
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19 326 process. We examined the infection structures of strains during the infection
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21 327 using scan electron microscope (SEM). Ultrastructural examination showed
22
23 328 that the hyphae of the wild type formed typical infection cushions on the
24
25 329 glumes at 48 h post-inoculation with conidia, but such penetration structures
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27 330 were not observed on the glumes inoculated with conidia of either $\Delta FgLetm1$
28
29 331 or $\Delta\Delta FgLetm1/2$ under the same conditions. Both $\Delta FgLetm2$ and the two
30
31 332 complemented strains showed similar infection structures on plant tissues to
32
33 333 those of the wild type (Fig. 6b). Noticeably, the $\Delta FgLetm1$ mutant was capable
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35 334 of penetrating the spikelet and resulted in the scab symptom after 2 weeks at
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37 335 the inoculated sites (Figs. 6a, S5). These results suggested that the $\Delta FgLetm1$
38
39 336 mutant delayed the penetration structure formation and was defective in
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41 337 spreading from the inoculation site to nearby spikelets *via* the rachis. We
42
43 338 conclude that $FgLetm1$ is important in virulence in *F. graminearum*.

339 **$FgLetm1$ plays a critical role in DON biosynthesis**

340 DON biosynthesis in the mutants was evaluated both *in vitro* and *in planta*.
341 First, the transcriptional levels of *TRI* genes in the mutants were assayed by
342 qRT-PCR in TBI. All selected *TRI* genes were strongly down-regulated in the

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3 343 Δ FgLetm1 mutant, but the expression was not affected in Δ FgLetm2,
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5 344 compared to those in the wild type (Fig. 7a). Next, the toxisome formation
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7 345 (Boenisch *et al.*, 2017) for DON biosynthesis in the wild type and the mutants
8
9 346 was observed using the Tri1-GFP as an indicator in TBI cultures. As shown in
10
11 347 Fig. 7b, the Tri1-GFP was highly induced and formed spherical and crescent
12
13 348 toxisomes in the mycelia of the wild type and the Δ FgLetm2 mutant after 3
14
15 349 days of incubation in TBI. However, no visible green fluorescent signals were
16
17 350 observed in the mycelia of Δ FgLetm1 under the same condition. Consistent
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19 351 with the expression of *TRI* genes and toxisomes formation, the amount of the
20
21 352 final product of DON biosynthesis in Δ FgLetm1 was strongly reduced by
22
23 353 18-fold when compared to that in the wild type in the TBI liquid medium
24
25 354 (Table 3). DON production was also significantly reduced in the Δ FgLetm1
26
27 355 deletion mutant in wheat grain cultures and the infested wheat kernels *in*
28
29 356 *planta*. The complemented strain Δ FgLetm1-C was completely restored in
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31 357 DON production (Table 3). Collectively, our results suggest that FgLetm1 is
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33 358 important in *TRI* gene expression and DON production in *F. graminearum*.

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38 359 To determine whether the DON reduction is caused by decreased ATP and
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40 360 ROS production in Δ FgLetm1, we conducted DON rescue assays by supplying
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42 361 exogenous ATP or H₂O₂ in the liquid cultures induced by ammonium as
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44 362 described previously (Gardiner *et al.*, 2009). Treatment with H₂O₂ clearly
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46 363 increased DON biosynthesis in PH-1, and partially recovered DON
47
48 364 biosynthesis in Δ FgLetm1 (Fig. 7c). However, the final production of DON after
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50 365 induction by H₂O₂ was still less than in the wild type (Fig. 7c). We next assayed
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52 366 the expression of *TRI5*, *TRI6* and *TRI10* with RNA samples isolated from
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54 367 hyphae of the wild-type and Δ FgLetm1 mutant with or without treatment of 0.5
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3 368 mM H₂O₂ in LTB at day 3. In the wild type strain, the expression levels of *TRI5*,
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5 369 *TRI6* and *TRI10* were 4.0-, 10.4- and 5.2-fold higher in H₂O₂-treated samples
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7 370 than in untreated samples (Fig. 7d). Treatment with H₂O₂ also induced the
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9 371 expression of these *TRI* genes in the Δ FgLetm1 mutant (Fig. 7d). However,
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11 372 addition of exogenous ATP in TBI was unable to rescue the decreased of DON
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13 373 biosynthesis in the Δ FgLetm1 mutant (Fig. S6). Therefore, our evidence
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15 374 implied that the diminished endogenous ROS might be partly responsible for
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17 375 the reduction of DON biosynthesis in Δ FgLetm1.
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21 376 **Wild type *F. graminearum* produced less DON and was strongly**
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23 377 **attenuated in virulence under the hypoxic condition.**

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25 378 Given that dysfunctional mitochondria in the Δ FgLetm1 mutant increased the
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27 379 activity of glycolysis, but decreased the DON biosynthesis and virulence, we
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29 380 speculated that DON biosynthesis might be suppressed under hypoxic
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31 381 condition. Therefore, we investigated DON biosynthesis and virulence of *F.*
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33 382 *graminearum* under the limited O₂ condition (1%). Surprisingly, the radial
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35 383 growth rate of the wild type PH-1 under hypoxic condition was similar to that
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37 384 under the open air condition (Fig. 8a). Compared with the expression of *TRI5*,
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39 385 *TRI6* and *TRI10* in TBI under the open air condition, the expression of these
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41 386 genes in the wild type was strongly reduced under the hypoxic condition (Fig.
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43 387 8b), which was similar levels to these in Δ FgLetm1 mutant (Fig. 7a). However,
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45 388 the transcriptional level of the control gene *AURJ* for pigment formation was
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47 389 increased under the hypoxic condition, indicating that the reduction of the *TRI*
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49 390 gene expression was somehow specific under the hypoxic condition.
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51 391 Meanwhile, the Tri1-GFP labeled toxosome formation was also completely
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53 392 abolished under the hypoxic condition (Fig. 8c). Finally, the DON production
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3 393 under hypoxic condition decreased by 40-fold than that in the open air (Fig. 8d).
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5 394 The pathogenicity assay was also conducted under both conditions. After 7
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7 395 days post-inoculation, the mycelia were able to infect the inoculated site,
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10 396 caused the necrotic symptom, and spread to nearby spikelets under the open
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12 397 air condition (Fig. 8e, left-hand panel). Remarkably, wild type PH-1 failed to
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14 398 infect the inoculate spikelet under the hypoxia condition (Fig. 8e, right-hand
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16 399 panel). Taken together, DON biosynthesis and virulence were suppressed in *F.*
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18 400 *graminearum* under the low oxygen conditions, similar to the effect of
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20 401 dysfunctional mitochondria caused by deletion of the *FgLETM1* gene.

402 **DISCUSSION**

403 Mdm38 in yeast is critical for the maintenance of mitochondrial morphology.
404 The lack or RNAi silencing of Letm1 orthologs led to the disruption of the
405 mitochondrial network and apparent swelling of the mitochondria in various
406 organisms (Dimmer *et al.*, 2002b, Nowikovsky *et al.*, 2004, Schlickum *et al.*,
407 2004, Sickmann *et al.*, 2003, Hasegawa & van der Bliik, 2007, McQuibban *et*
408 *al.*, 2010, Hashimi *et al.*, 2013). To date, no study has been conducted to
409 investigate the biological roles of the Letm1 orthologs in filamentous fungi. In
410 this study, we showed that the $\Delta FgLetm1$ mutant of the filamentous fungus *F.*
411 *graminearum* lacked tubular-shaped cristae structures and had increased
412 mitochondrial volumes (Fig. 4b-c). Interestingly, for the first time, we also
413 showed that *FgLetm1* plays an important role in mitochondrial mobility, since
414 the $\Delta FgLetm1$ mutation slows down the dynamic change of mitochondria
415 (Videos S1-2). Mdm38 in *S. cerevisiae* also plays a critical role in the
416 biogenesis of the respiratory chain by coupling ribosome function to protein
417 transport across the inner membrane (Frazier *et al.*, 2006, Tamai *et al.*, 2008).

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3 418 Here, we found that the protein synthesis of cytochrome *b* decreased in the
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5 419 Δ FgLetm1 mutant (Fig. 4d). To support this idea, we conducted an affinity
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7 420 capture assay with the FgLetm1-GFP fusion protein as a bait. Protein mass
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9 421 spectrometry data showed that 18 proteins of the mitochondrial ribosome were
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11 422 associated with FgLetm1 (Table S2). Among them, 12 homologous proteins
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13 423 were also found in complex with Mdm38 and Ylh47 by affinity purification in
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15 424 yeast (Frazier et al., 2006). Taken together, the roles of the Letm1 super-family
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17 425 proteins in mitochondrial integrity and the biogenesis of the respiratory chain
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19 426 seem to be highly conserved from yeast to mammals, although their amino
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21 427 acid sequence and motif features differ among each other.

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25 428 In addition, we also found that FgLetm1 *in F. graminearum* had some
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27 429 distinct features from their orthologs in other organisms. For instance, Mdm38
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29 430 is required for efficient growth on non-fermentable carbon sources, such as
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31 431 glycerol, in yeast (Frazier et al., 2006). In contrast, the Δ FgLetm1 mutant of *F.*
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33 432 *graminearum* showed a comparable growth phenotype on agar media
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35 433 supplemented with either glucose or glycerol as the sole carbon source (Fig.
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37 434 S7). Deletion of Δ FgLetm1 was strongly decreased the conidiation and septum
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39 435 of conidia, and reduced stress response towards fungicides, ions and oxidative
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41 436 stress. These results implied that FgLetm1 is critical for fitness in certain
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43 437 environmental niches. Therefore, FgLetm1 may have species-specific
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45 438 activities, in addition to the conserved function of Letm1 orthologs in
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47 439 maintaining the integrity of mitochondria.

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50 440 Reactive oxygen species (ROS) play a major role in pathogen-plant
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52 441 interactions, during which the host plant rapidly triggers an oxidative burst to
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54 442 suppress a pathogen infection. Pathogens have to cope with plant-released
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3 443 ROS during a successful infection (Apel & Hirt, 2004, Heller & Tudzynski,
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5 444 2011). Most likely, all organisms have evolved oxidative stress response (OSR)
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7 445 mechanisms to scavenge elevated intracellular ROS levels. The ROS
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10 446 scavenging system is important for the detoxification of ROS in the cells, and
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12 447 the OSR has to be tightly regulated. In budding yeast, several signal
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14 448 components are involved in the regulation of the OSR at the transcriptional
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16 449 level, including the Hog1 cascade and the transcription factors Yap1, Atf1 and
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18 450 Skn7 (He & Fassler, 2005, Kim & Hahn, 2013, Raitt *et al.*, 2000). In *F.*
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20 451 *graminearum*, all three stress-related transcription factor genes, *FgAP1*,
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22 452 *FgATF1* and *FgSKN7*, play a role in the tolerance of oxidative stress.
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25 453 Moreover, *F. graminearum* has evolved its OSR system to transduce oxidative
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27 454 stress as a signal for the induction of DON biosynthesis, which is a critical
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29 455 virulence factor during the infection process (Jiang *et al.*, 2015, Montibus *et al.*,
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31 456 2013, Van Nguyen *et al.*, 2013). A supplement of H₂O₂ in the cell culture of *F.*
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33 457 *graminearum* stimulated *TRI* gene expression and increased DON
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35 458 accumulation, in a manner largely dependent on the OSR transcription factor
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37 459 FgSKN7 (Jiang *et al.*, 2015). In addition to treatment of exogenous ROS,
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39 460 endogenous ROS also modulates DON production. H₂O₂ was shown to
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41 461 constitutively accumulate in the DON induction medium in the culture of *F.*
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43 462 *graminearum*. Moreover, the time course curve of H₂O₂ accumulation followed
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45 463 the pattern of DON production (Ponts *et al.*, 2006, Ponts *et al.*, 2007).
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47 464 Consistence with above findings, we found that ROS was highly accumulated
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49 465 in the mycotoxin induction medium (TBI), and exogenous H₂O₂ was stimulated
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51 466 the DON production (Figs. 5, 7). We also found that deletion of *FgLETM1*
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53 467 almost completely abolished ROS production in mitochondria in MM and TBI
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3 468 media (Fig. 5a, Table 2), and caused the reduction of DON biosynthesis both *in*
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5 469 *vitro* and *in planta* (Table 3). The expression of *TRI* genes and DON production
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7 470 in $\Delta FgLetm1$ were partially rescued in the LTB medium supplemented with
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9 471 H_2O_2 (Figs. 7c-d). Therefore, the mitochondria-derived ROS was important for
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11 472 the DON biosynthesis in *F. graminearum*, although other factors related to
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13 473 mitochondrial dysfunction might also be involved in this process
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16 474 (Bonnighausen *et al.*, 2015).

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19 475 The concentration of oxygen in the atmosphere is important for the
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21 476 biosynthesis of mycotoxins. *Penicillium griseofulvum* produced less of the
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23 477 patulin toxin in 1% or 5% O_2 environment than in open air (20% O_2) (Paster &
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25 478 Lisker, 1985). Ans another example, only trace amounts of T-2 toxin was
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27 479 detected in *Fusarium sporotrichioides* under 40% $CO_2/5\% O_2$, in comparison
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29 480 with a much greater amount of T-2 toxin under 40% $CO_2/20\% O_2$ (Paster *et al.*,
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31 481 1986). Fungal growth in these gaseous environments was identical to that
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33 482 under the open air condition, even in O_2 concentrations of <1% (Hocking,
34
35 483 1989).. Here we found that *F. graminearum* showed normal growth patterns in
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37 484 the 1% O_2 condition as in the open air condition (Fig. 8a), but low levels of
38
39 485 oxygen strongly reduced DON production and virulence (Fig. 8b-e), similar to
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41 486 the phenotypes seen in the $\Delta FgLetm1$ mutant (Figs. 6, 7). On the other hand,
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43 487 disruption of the mitochondrial integrity in $\Delta FgLetm1$ significantly reduced the
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45 488 DON production (Fig. 7, table 3). We infer that fungicides targeting the
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47 489 mitochondria might possess a potential role in controlling the DON
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49 490 biosynthesis and FHB. We thus evaluated the effect of three mitochondrial
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51 491 targeting fungicides including boscalid, pyraclostrobin and py-diflumetofen on
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53 492 the DON production. As expected, all three tested fungicides strongly reduced
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3 493 the DON production (Fig. S8). Taken together, our results suggested that
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5 494 storage of grain under hypoxia and fungicides targeting mitochondria might
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7 495 provide potential approaches for DON management.
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11 497 **EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES**

12 498 **Fungal strains and culture conditions**

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16 499 *Fusarium graminearum* strain PH-1 (NRRL 31084) was used as the progenitor
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18 500 for constructing gene deletion mutants. The wild type and transformants
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21 501 generated in this study were grown at 25 °C on potato dextrose agar, minimal
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23 502 medium, and wheat-head medium for mycelial growth tests (Liu et al., 2015).
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25 503 CMC media was used for sporulation assays (Cappelli.Ra & Peterson, 1965).
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27 504 For quantifying the DON production, strains were grown in liquid TBI medium
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29 505 (Menke *et al.*, 2012). To evaluate the effect of H₂O₂ on the induction of DON
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31 506 biosynthesis, wild type or mutants were cultured in the LTB as described
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34 507 (Jiang *et al.*, 2016), and H₂O₂ was supplemented at a final concentration of 0.5
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36 508 mM. For hypoxia condition, the inoculated TBI or wheat heads were statically
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38 509 incubated in a modular incubator chamber (billups-rothenberg, Inc) filled with
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40 510 mixture gases (1% O₂, 99% N₂).

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42
43 511 The sensitivity of strains towards stress agents was determined as
44
45 512 described previously (Liu et al., 2015). The final concentration of NaCl, KCl,
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47 513 and fungicides, Fe²⁺, CaCl₂ and H₂O₂ in MM were indicated in the figure. For
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49 514 testing the temperature sensitivity of the mutants, cells were grown at 15 °C,
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51 515 25 °C and 32 °C. The mycelial growth inhibition rate (MGIR) was calculated
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53 516 using the formula MGIR% = [(N-C)/C]*100, where, C is colony diameter of the
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56 517 control without treatment, and N is that with treatment. Each experiment was
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3 518 repeated three times independently.
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5 **519 Construction of gene deletion mutants and complemented strains**
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7 520 Construction of gene deletion and complementation vectors and subsequent
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9 521 transformation of *F. graminearum* were carried out using the protocols
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11 522 described previously (Jiang *et al.*, 2011). In order to generate double mutant of
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13 523 *FgLETM1* and *FgLETM2*, *FgLETM1* was knocked out in the *FgLETM2* deletion
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16 524 mutant (Δ FgLETM2). The primers used to amplify the flanking sequences of
17
18 525 each gene are listed in Table S3. Deletion candidates were identified by PCR
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21 526 with designated primers (Table S3), and were further analyzed by Southern
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23 527 blotting. Three independent transformants for each mutant were used in all
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25 528 experiments. FgLetm1-GFP, FgLetm2-GFP, Tri1-GFP and FgAtg8-RFP fusion
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27 529 constructs were generated as described previously (Gu *et al.*, 2015a).
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30 **530 Plant infection and DON production assays**
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32 531 A 10- μ l aliquot of conidial suspension (1×10^5 conidia/ml) was injected into a
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34 532 floret in the central section spikelet of single flowering wheat head of
35
36 533 susceptible cultivar grown in the field. There were ten replicates for each strain.
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38 534 Fifteen days after inoculation, the infected spikelets in each inoculated wheat
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40 535 head were recorded. The experiment was repeated four times, and typical
41
42 536 symptom was shown. Infectious hyphae developed in wheat tissue cells were
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45 537 examined at 48 h post-inoculation by SEM.
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48 538 The strain expressing the Tri1-GFP was used as the fluorescent reporter
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50 539 strain for toxisome formation, and toxisome formation was observed after 3
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52 540 days of incubation in TBI. The DON production in the wild type, the mutants
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54 541 and complemented strains were quantified under several conditions, including
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56 542 the TBI, LTB, wheat kernel medium and inoculated spikelets. The supernatant
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3 543 of TBI after 7-day incubation was collected for quantification of DON. DON
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5 544 production in wheat kernel medium was conducted as described previously
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7 545 (Liu et al., 2015, Ji *et al.*, 2014). The inoculated spikelets were harvested after
8
9 546 fifteen days, and DON was extracted as described (Jiang et al., 2015). Total
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11 547 amount of ergosterol was extracted from infected spikelets as described (Liu et
12
13 548 al., 2013). For ROS induction assay, LTB was used for replacement of TBI,
14
15 549 since the DON biosynthesis was already extremely induced. Recipe of LTB
16
17 550 medium was modified from TBI, only replacing the putrescine to ammonium
18
19 551 nitrate at the final concentration of 5 mM. H₂O₂ was daily added into the LTB to
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21 552 the final concentration of 0.5 mM. After 7 days of incubation, the supernatant
22
23 553 was collected for DON quantification. DON samples were quantified by
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25 554 LC-MS/MS as described previously (Dong *et al.*, 2016). The experiment was
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27 555 repeated three times.
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32 **qRT-PCR assays**

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34 557 RNA samples of the wild type, mutants and complemented strains were
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36 558 isolated as described (Liu et al., 2015). For the induction of *TRI* genes by H₂O₂,
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38 559 the hyphae of wild type or mutant were harvested for RNA extraction after 48 h
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40 560 of treatment. TAKARA SYBR Premix Ex Taq was used for qRT-PCR assays
41
42 561 with the CFX96 Real-Time System as described (Bio-RAD, USA). The actin
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44 562 gene of *F. graminearum* was used as the internal control. Relative expression
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46 563 levels of each gene were calculated with the $2^{-\Delta\Delta Ct}$ method (Livak &
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48 564 Schmittgen, 2001).
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51 **Western blotting hybridization**

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53 566 The protein extraction and Western blot analysis were performed as described
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55 567 previously (Yun *et al.*, 2015). Anti-MT-CYB antibody (Abcam, ab103405) was
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3 568 used to detect the cytochrome b for analyzing the biosynthesis of the
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5 569 respiratory chain. The samples were also detected with monoclonal anti-H3
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7 570 antibody (Abcam, ab1791) as a reference. The mCherry-FgAtg8 proteolysis
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9 571 was quantified by western blots with anti-mCherry antibody (Abcam,
10
11 572 ab167453). The samples were also detected with monoclonal anti-GAPDH
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13 573 antibody EM1101 (Hangzhou HuaAn Biotechnology co., Ltd.) as a reference.
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16 574 All experiments were conducted three times.

17 18 575 **Microscopy imaging**

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21 576 Localization of green fluorescent labeled proteins and Mito-HcRed (Thermo
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23 577 Fisher, M7512) staining signals were visualized by the Zeiss LSM780 confocal
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25 578 microscope (Carl Zeiss AG, Germany). The microstructure of mitochondria in
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27 579 wild type or mutants was treated as described (Yun et al., 2015) and observed
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29 580 by the transmission electron microscope (TEM) JEOL JEM-1230. For
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31 581 observation of infection structures on wheat glumes, the glumes were treated
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33 582 as previous described (Gu *et al.*, 2015b), and observed in Hitachi Model
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35 583 TM-1000 scan electron microscope (SEM) (Hitachi, Tokyo, Japan).

36 37 38 584 **Quantification of ATP and H₂O₂ production**

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41 585 The mycelia grown in MM for 24 h and in TBI for 3 days were used for
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43 586 quantification of H₂O₂ and ATP. H₂O₂ and ATP production were assayed using
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45 587 the Hydrogen Peroxide Assay Kit (Beyotime Institute of Biotechnology, China,
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47 588 S0038) and ATP Assay Kit (Beyotime, S0026), respectively. Briefly, mycelia
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49 589 (0.05 g) were added to 200 µl of the lysis buffer in the H₂O₂ detection kit or 500
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51 590 µl of the lysis buffer in the ATP detection kit. After lysis of mycelia,
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53 591 quantification of H₂O₂ or ATP production was conducted following the
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3 592 instructions provided by the manufacturer. Experiments were repeated three
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5 593 times.

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10 595 **ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS**

11 596 We thank Dr. Jiang Cong and Dr. Huiquan Liu (Northwest A&F University) for
12
13 597 DON quantification and bioinformatics analyses, Prof. Yunrong Chai
14
15 598 (Northeastern University, Boston) and Kevin Gozzi (Massachusetts Institute of
16
17 599 Technology) for manuscript editing. The research was supported by the
20
21 600 Natural Science Foundation of Zhejiang Province (LR17C140001), National
22
23 601 Natural Science Foundation of China (31672064), International Science &
24
25 602 Technology Cooperation Program of China (2016YFE0112900) and China
26
27 603 Agriculture Research System (CARS-3-1-15). The authors declare no conflict
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29 604 of interest.
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3 817 **Figure legends**

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5 818 **Fig. 1. Identification of the Letm1-like proteins in *Fusarium graminearum*.**

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7 819 **a.** Schematic architecture of the Letm1 super-family proteins in *F.*
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9 *graminearum*, FgLetm1 and FgLetm2. The *Homo sapiens* Letm1 and *S.*
10 *cerevisiae* Mdm38 and Ylh47 are selected as references. Conserved domains
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12 821 are indicated. **b.** Phylogenetic analysis of the putative Letm1-like proteins from
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14 822 *F. graminearum* and six plant pathogenic fungi. Amino acid sequences of the
15
16 823 Letm1 orthologs are aligned using Clustal W and a neighbor-joining tree
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18 824 generated by MEGA 5.0. **c.** Transcriptional levels of the *FgLETM1* and
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20 825 *FgLETM2* genes in the CMC, hyphae, infected plant tissues and TBI by
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22 826 RNA-seq.

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27 828 **Fig. 2. Phenotypes of the deletion mutants of Δ FgLetm1, Δ FgLetm2 and**
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29 829 **$\Delta\Delta$ FgLetm1/2 in vegetative growth, conidiogenesis and germination.**

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31
32 830 **a.** Colony morphology of PH-1, the mutants and the complemented strains on
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34 831 PDA and MM at 25 °C for 3 days. **b.** Ratio of the different number of conidial
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36 832 septa in PH-1, mutants and complemented strains harvested from 5-day-old
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38 833 CMC cultures. **c.** Δ FgLetm1 reduced the conidial germination. The column
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40 834 labeled with star indicates a significant difference at $P = 0.05$.

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42
43 835 **Fig. 3. Δ FgLetm1 increased the sensitivity towards osmotic stress, heat**
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45 836 **shock, fungicides and ion stresses.**

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47 837 **a.** Growth phenotype of PH-1, mutants and complemented strains grown on
48
49 838 MM without or with supplementation of NaCl or KCl after 4 days of incubation
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51 839 at 25 °C. **b.** Statistical analysis of the growth inhibition rate of all strains under
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53 840 the osmotic stresses. **c.** Δ FgLetm1 increased the sensitivity toward high
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55 841 temperature. Colony morphology was shown after 4 days of incubation on MM
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3 842 at 15 °C and 25 °C, and 7 days of incubation at 32 °C. **d.** The transcriptional
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5 843 level of the heat tolerant genes *FgHSP30*, *FgHSP70* and *FgGSY2* decreased
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7 844 in the Δ FgLetm1 mutant in response to heat shock, in comparison to that in
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9 845 PH-1. The expression levels of each gene at 25 °C for 16 h were set to 1. **e.**
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11 846 The Δ FgLetm1 mutant was more sensitive towards fungicides iprodione,
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13 847 phenamacril, and ion stresses than that of the wild type. Plates were incubated
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15 848 at 25 °C for 4 days before imaging. **f.** Statistical analysis of the growth
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17 849 inhibition rate of strains towards above stresses. Values on the bars followed
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19 850 by the same letter mean no significant difference at $P = 0.05$.

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23 851 **Fig. 4. FgLetm1 is localized to mitochondria and critical for the**
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25 852 **mitochondrial integrity.**

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27 853 **a.** Both FgLetm1 and FgLetm2 are localized to the mitochondria. Mycelia of
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29 854 FgLetm1-C and FgLetm2-C were grown in CM and stained with Mito-HcRed.
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31 855 Images were taken by confocal fluorescent microscope. Bar=10 μ m. **b.**
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33 856 Δ FgLetm1 changed the mitochondrial structural patterns. Strains were grown
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35 857 in CM broth for 16 h at 25 °C, then harvested and stained with Mito-HcRed for
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37 858 observation. Typical patterns in individual strain were shown. Bar= 10 μ m. **c.**
38
39 859 Δ FgLetm1 mutant caused mitochondrial swelling. Ultrastructural morphology
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41 860 of mitochondria in each strain was visualized by transmission electron
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43 861 microscope. Bars were indicated in images. **d.** Δ FgLetm1 decreased the
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45 862 protein level of cytochrome *b* (Cyt *b*), an indicator protein of respiratory chain
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47 863 components. The protein abundance of Cyt *b* in the PH-1 and mutants were
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49 864 analyzed by immunoblot assays. The histone H3 was used as a reference
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51 865 protein.

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53 866 **Fig. 5. Deletion mutant of Δ FgLetm1 decreased the concentration of**
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3 867 **endogenous reactive oxygen species (ROS).**

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5 868 **a.** $\Delta FgLetm1$ strongly reduced the endogenous ROS in MM and TBI. Hyphae
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7 869 grown in MM for 24 h, or TBI for 3 days were stained by the ROS indicator,
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9 870 H2DCFDA. Bar=10 μm . **b.** Mutant of $\Delta FgLetm1$ and $\Delta\Delta FgLetm1/2$ decreased
10
11 871 the transcriptional level of genes encoding catalases and superoxide
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13 872 dismutases in TBI. **c.** Mutant of $\Delta FgLetm1$ and $\Delta\Delta FgLetm1/2$ increased the
14
15 873 resistance towards the oxidative stress by H_2O_2 . Strains were grown on MM
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17 874 with or without 10 mM H_2O_2 for 4 days at 25°C. **d.** Statistical analysis of the
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19 875 growth inhibition rate of PH-1, mutants and complemented strains towards the
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21 876 oxidative stress generated by H_2O_2 . Values on the bars followed by the same
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23 877 letter indicate no significant difference at $P = 0.01$.

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25 878 **Fig. 6 Deletion mutants of $\Delta FgLetm1$ and $\Delta\Delta FgLetm1/2$ were attenuated**
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27 879 **in virulence *in planta*.**

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29 880 **a.** Dissection of infected wheat heads caused by PH-1, the mutants and the
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31 881 complemented strains. Inoculated ears were dissected at 15 dpi. Inoculated
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33 882 sites were indicated with red arrows. **b.** Infection structures on glumes infected
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35 883 by PH-1, mutants and complemented strains. The inoculated glumes were
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37 884 collected after 2 dpi with conidia, and observed by SEM. The infection
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39 885 structures were pointed out by red arrows, and details were enlarged.

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41 886 **Fig. 7. Deletion mutants of $\Delta FgLetm1$ and $\Delta\Delta FgLetm1/2$ reduced the DON**
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43 887 **biosynthesis *in vitro* and *in planta*.**

44
45 888 **a.** $\Delta FgLetm1$ significantly decreased the transcriptional level of *TRI* genes in
46
47 889 TBI medium. **b.** Toxisome formation of PH-1, $\Delta FgLetm1$ and $\Delta FgLetm2$.
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49 890 Strains were labeled with Tri1-GFP and incubated in TBI for 3 days, and
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51 891 toxisomes were observed by confocal fluorescent microscope. Bar=10 μm . **c.**

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3 892 Induction of DON biosynthesis by H₂O₂ in wild type and ΔFgLetm1 grown in
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5 893 LTB medium. H₂O₂ was added into LTB daily, and the supernatant after 7 days
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7 894 of incubation was used for the quantification of DON production. **d.** Relative
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9 895 expression levels of *TRI5*, *TRI6* and *TRI10* in PH-1 and ΔFgLetm1 with or
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11 896 without H₂O₂ treatment. The relative expression level of each gene in wild type
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13 897 without H₂O₂ treatment was arbitrarily set to 1. Values on the bars followed by
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15 898 the same letter indicate no significant difference at *P* = 0.05.

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18 899 **Fig. 8. DON biosynthesis and virulence were reduced under hypoxia**
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21 900 **conditions.**

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23 901 **a.** Colony morphology of wild type grown on PDA in the open air and hypoxia
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25 902 conditions. **b.** Relative expression level of *TRI5*, *TRI6* and *TRI10* in the
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27 903 mycelium of PH-1 under open air and hypoxia conditions. Strains were grown
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29 904 in TBI for 3 days. The pigment biosynthesis gene, *AURJ*, was used as a
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31 905 control. **c.** Toxisome formation of the wild type under open air and hypoxia
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33 906 conditions. The Tri1-GFP was observed after 3 days of incubation. **d.** DON
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35 907 production of wild type under open air and hypoxia conditions after 7 days of
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37 908 incubation. **e.** Virulence of wild type under open air and hypoxia conditions.
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40 909 Scab symptom was taken after 7 dpi.
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3 910 **Supplemental figure, table and video legends**

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5 911 **Fig. S1. Phylogenetic tree of the Letm1 super-family orthologs from 32**
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7 912 **fungal genomes available in the NCBI Bioprojects and Broad Institute**

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10 913 **databases.** Orthologs were retrieved with the yeast Letm1 proteins, Mdm38
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12 914 and Ylh47, and FgLetm1 and FgLetm2 protein sequences as queries. The
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14 915 phylogenetic tree was constructed by the neighbor-joining method using
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16 916 MEGA 5.0. Numbers at the node represent the results of 1000 bootstrap
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18 917 replications. The GenBank or organism-specific accession numbers are
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21 918 indicated in the figure.

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23 919 **Fig. S2. Identification of deletion mutants and complemented strains.**

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25 920 **a.** Southern blot hybridization analysis of the deletion mutant of Δ FgLetm1,
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27 921 $\Delta\Delta$ FgLetm1/2, and the complemented strain Δ FgLetm1+P_{LETM1} FgLetm1-GFP
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29 922 using downstream DNA fragments of *FgLETM1* as the probe. Both Δ FgLetm1
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31 923 and $\Delta\Delta$ FgLetm1/2 had an anticipated 4594 bp band, but both of them lacked
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33 924 the 2219 bp band present in wild-type PH-1, when probed with a 725 bp
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35 925 downstream DNA fragment of *FgLETM1*. **b.** Southern blot hybridization
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37 926 analysis of the deletion mutant of Δ FgLetm2, $\Delta\Delta$ FgLetm1/2, and the
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39 927 complemented strain Δ FgLetm2+P_{LETM2} FgLetm2-GFP using a downstream
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41 928 DNA fragment of *FgLETM2* as the probe. Using an 800 bp upstream DNA
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43 929 fragment of *FgLETM2* as the probe, Δ FgLetm2 mutant had an anticipated
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45 930 3253 bp band, when the chromosomal DNA of Δ FgLetm2 was digested with
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47 931 *NdeI*. $\Delta\Delta$ FgLetm1/2 presented a 4098 bp band but lacked the 1585 bp band
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49 932 present in the wild-type PH-1, when the chromosomal DNA of $\Delta\Delta$ FgLetm1/2
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51 933 was digested with *EcoRV* and blotted with the same probe. **c.** PCR verification
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53 934 of complemented strain Δ FgLetm1+P_{LETM1} FgLetm1-GFP, and
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3 935 Δ FgLetm2+P_{LETM2}FgLetm2-GFP. The whole cassette including the promoter,
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5 936 ORF and gfp was amplified, respectively.
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7 937 **Fig. S3. Conidial morphology of the wild type, Δ FgLetm1, Δ FgLetm2,**
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9 938 **$\Delta\Delta$ FgLetm1/2 and the complemented strains.** The septa were stained with
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11 939 calcofluor white and observed by fluorescent microscope. Bar= 20 μ m.
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14 940 **Fig. S4. Colony morphology of PH-1, the mutants and the complemented**
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16 941 **strains on wheat head medium (WA) at 25 °C for 3 days.**
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18 942 **Fig. S5. Infection structure of wild type and deletion mutant of Δ FgLetm1**
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20 943 **on the inoculated glumes at 14 days post-inoculation.** Samples were
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22 944 collected after 2 weeks post-inoculation and observed by the scan electron
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24 945 microscope. Bars were indicated on the images.
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27 946 **Fig. S6. Induction of DON biosynthesis by exogenous ATP in the wild**
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29 947 **type and mutants grown in TBI medium.** ATP was added into TBI with at the
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31 948 final concentration of 10 μ M, and the cell free supernatant after 7 days of
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33 949 incubation was used for the quantification of DON production. Error bars
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35 950 denote standard deviation from three repeated experiments.
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38 951 **Fig. S7. Deletion mutant of Δ FgLetm1 was not changed the utilization of**
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40 952 **non-fermentable carbon.** Colony morphology of the wild type, Δ FgLetm1,
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42 953 Δ FgLetm2 and $\Delta\Delta$ FgLetm1/2 on minimal medium supplemented with glucose
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44 954 or glycerol as a sole carbon source. Plates were photographed after incubation
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46 955 at 25 °C for 3 days.
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49 956 **Fig. S8. Fungicides targeting mitochondria are able to inhibit the**
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51 957 **toxisome formation and DON biosynthesis.**
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54 958 **a.** The growth inhibition of tested fungicides at 0.3 μ g/ml. **b.** Toxisome
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56 959 formation of fungicides at 0.3 μ g/ml. The Δ Tri1:Tri1-GFP strain was grown in
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3 960 TBI for 24 h, then individual fungicide was added at the final concentration at
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5 961 0.3 µg/ml and incubated for another 24 h before observation. c. The DON
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7 962 production of each treatment. The DON was extracted from the 7-day cultured
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10 963 TBI in each treatment and quantified by LC-MS. Column followed by different
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12 964 letter indicated a significantly difference at $P = 0.05$.

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14 965 **Table S1** The Letm1-superfamily domain in the Letm1 orthologues of 6
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16 966 filamentous plant pathogenic fungi and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*.

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18 967 **Table S2** Proteins of the mitochondrial ribosome in complex with FgLetm1 by
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20 968 affinity purification and mass spectrometry assay.

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23 969 **Table S3.** Oligonucleotide primers used in this study.

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25 970 **Video 1.** Mitochondrial patterns stained by Mito-HcRed in the wild type.

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27 971 **Video 2.** Mitochondrial patterns stained by Mito-HcRed in deletion mutant of
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29 972 Δ FgLetm1.
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Fig. 1. Identification of the Letm1-like proteins in *Fusarium graminearum*. a. Schematic architecture of the Letm1 super-family proteins in *F. graminearum*, FgLetm1 and FgLetm2. The *Homo sapiens* Letm1 and *S. cerevisiae* Mdm38 and Ylh47 are selected as references. Conserved domains are indicated. b. Phylogenetic analysis of the putative Letm1-like proteins from *F. graminearum* and six plant pathogenic fungi. Amino acid sequences of the Letm1 orthologs are aligned using Clustal W and a neighbor-joining tree generated by MEGA 5.0. c. Transcriptional levels of the FgLETM1 and FgLETM2 genes in the CMC, hyphae, infected plant tissues and TBI by RNA-seq.

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Fig. 2. Phenotypes of the deletion mutants of $\Delta FgLetm1$, $\Delta FgLetm2$ and $\Delta\Delta FgLetm1/2$ in vegetative growth, conidiogenesis and germination.

a. Colony morphology of PH-1, the mutants and the complemented strains on PDA and MM at 25 °C for 3 days. b. Ratio of the different number of conidial septa in PH-1, mutants and complemented strains harvested from 5-day-old CMC cultures. c. $\Delta FgLetm1$ reduced the conidial germination. The column labeled with star indicates a significant difference at $P = 0.05$.

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Fig. 3. Δ FgLetm1 increased the sensitivity towards osmotic stress, heat shock, fungicides and ion stresses. a. Growth phenotype of PH-1, mutants and complemented strains grown on MM without or with supplementation of NaCl or KCl after 4 days of incubation at 25 °C. b. Statistical analysis of the growth inhibition rate of all strains under the osmotic stresses. c. Δ FgLetm1 increased the sensitivity toward high temperature. Colony morphology was shown after 4 days of incubation on MM at 15 °C and 25 °C, and 7 days of incubation at 32 °C. d. The transcriptional level of the heat tolerant genes FgHSP30, FgHSP70 and FgGSY2 decreased in the Δ FgLetm1 mutant in response to heat shock, in comparison to that in PH-1. The expression levels of each gene at 25 °C for 16 h were set to 1. e. The Δ FgLetm1 mutant was more sensitive towards fungicides iprodione, phenamacril, and ion stresses than that of the wild type. Plates were incubated at 25 °C for 4 days before imaging. f. Statistical analysis of the growth inhibition rate of strains towards above stresses. Values on the bars followed by the same letter mean no significant difference at $P = 0.05$.

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Fig. 4. FgLetm1 is localized to mitochondria and critical for the mitochondrial integrity. a. Both FgLetm1 and FgLetm2 are localized to the mitochondria. Mycelia of FgLetm1-C and FgLetm2-C were grown in CM and stained with Mito-HcRed. Images were taken by confocal fluorescent microscope. Bar=10 μ m. b. Δ FgLetm1 changed the mitochondrial structural patterns. Strains were grown in CM broth for 16 h at 25 $^{\circ}$ C, then harvested and stained with Mito-HcRed for observation. Typical patterns in individual strain were shown. Bar= 10 μ m. c. Δ FgLetm1 mutant caused mitochondrial swelling. Ultrastructural morphology of mitochondria in each strain was visualized by transmission electron microscope. Bars were indicated in images. d. Δ FgLetm1 decreased the protein level of cytochrome b (Cyt b), an indicator protein of respiratory chain components. The protein abundance of Cyt b in the PH-1 and mutants were analyzed by immunoblot assays. The histone H3 was used as a reference protein.

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Fig. 5. Deletion mutant of Δ FgLetm1 decreased the concentration of endogenous reactive oxygen species (ROS).

a. Δ FgLetm1 strongly reduced the endogenous ROS in MM and TBI. Hyphae grown in MM for 24 h, or TBI for 3 days were stained by the ROS indicator, H₂DCFDA. Bar=10 μ m. b. Mutant of Δ FgLetm1 and $\Delta\Delta$ FgLetm1/2 decreased the transcriptional level of genes encoding catalases and superoxide dismutases in TBI. c. Mutant of Δ FgLetm1 and $\Delta\Delta$ FgLetm1/2 increased the resistance towards the oxidative stress by H₂O₂. Strains were grown on MM with or without 10 mM H₂O₂ for 4 days at 25°C. d. Statistical analysis of the growth inhibition rate of PH-1, mutants and complemented strains towards the oxidative stress generated by H₂O₂. Values on the bars followed by the same letter indicate no significant difference at P = 0.01.

170x198mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Fig. 6 Deletion mutants of Δ FgLetm1 and $\Delta\Delta$ FgLetm1/2 were attenuated in virulence in planta.
 a. Dissection of infected wheat heads caused by PH-1, the mutants and the complemented strains. Inoculated ears were dissected at 15 dpi. Inoculated sites were indicated with red arrows. b. Infection structures on glumes infected by PH-1, mutants and complemented strains. The inoculated glumes were collected after 2 dpi with conidia, and observed by SEM. The infection structures were pointed out by red arrows, and details were enlarged.

170x157mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Fig. 7. Deletion mutants of $\Delta FgLetm1$ and $\Delta\Delta FgLetm1/2$ reduced the DON biosynthesis in vitro and in planta.

a. $\Delta FgLetm1$ significantly decreased the transcriptional level of TRI genes in TBI medium. b. Toxisome formation of PH-1, $\Delta FgLetm1$ and $\Delta FgLetm2$. Strains were labeled with Tri1-GFP and incubated in TBI for 3 days, and toxisomes were observed by confocal fluorescent microscope. Bar=10 μ m. c. Induction of DON biosynthesis by H₂O₂ in wild type and $\Delta FgLetm1$ grown in LTB medium. H₂O₂ was added into LTB daily, and the supernatant after 7 days of incubation was used for the quantification of DON production. d. Relative expression levels of TRI5, TRI6 and TRI10 in PH-1 and $\Delta FgLetm1$ with or without H₂O₂ treatment. The relative expression level of each gene in wild type without H₂O₂ treatment was arbitrarily set to 1. Values on the bars followed by the same letter indicate no significant difference at P = 0.05.

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Fig. 8. DON biosynthesis and virulence were reduced under hypoxia conditions.

a. Colony morphology of wild type grown on PDA in the open air and hypoxia conditions. b. Relative expression level of *TRI15*, *TRI6* and *TRI10* in the mycelium of PH-1 under open air and hypoxia conditions.

Strains were grown in TBI for 3 days. The pigment biosynthesis gene, *AURJ*, was used as a control. c. Toxisome formation of the wild type under open air and hypoxia conditions. The *Tri1*-GFP was observed after 3 days of incubation. d. DON production of wild type under open air and hypoxia conditions after 7 days of incubation. e. Virulence of wild type under open air and hypoxia conditions. Scab symptom was taken after 7 dpi.

80x62mm (300 x 300 DPI)

1 **Table 1 Vegetative growth and conidiation of *Fusarium graminearum***
 2 **strains**

Strain	Growth rate (cm/day)	Conidiation Production ($\times 10^5$)	Conidial length (μm)
PH-1	2.43 \pm 0.06 ^a *	6.15 \pm 0.47 ^a	63.50 \pm 6.10 ^a
Δ FgLetm1	2.06 \pm 0.03 ^b	4.65 \pm 0.53 ^b	38.88 \pm 4.39 ^b
Δ FgLetm1-C	2.40 \pm 0.04 ^a	6.28 \pm 0.48 ^a	63.13 \pm 8.04 ^a
Δ FgLetm2	2.32 \pm 0.02 ^a	6.03 \pm 0.38 ^a	56.50 \pm 5.07 ^a
Δ FgLetm2-C	2.37 \pm 0.02 ^a	5.98 \pm 0.26 ^a	59.88 \pm 2.10 ^a
Δ FgLetm12	2.03 \pm 0.03 ^b	5.20 \pm 0.34 ^b	41.25 \pm 3.57 ^b

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 4 *Values followed by the same letter are not significantly different at $P = 0.05$ for each
 5 treatment.

Proof

Table 2 Productions of ATP, hydrogen peroxide and ethanol in PH-1, mutants and complemented strains

Strain	ATP (μM)		H_2O_2 (mM)		Ethanol (mg/ml)
	MM	TBI	MM	TBI	MM
PH-1	1341.35 \pm 29.24 ^{a*}	1360.05 \pm 42.46 ^a	24.97 \pm 2.14 ^a	133.94 \pm 9.85 ^a	2.16 \pm 0.07 ^b
$\Delta\text{FgLetm1}$	1008.54 \pm 34.32 ^b	902.17 \pm 23.46 ^b	3.26 \pm 0.18 ^b	4.51 \pm 0.36 ^b	4.32 \pm 0.12 ^a
$\Delta\text{FgLetm1-C}$	1320.14 \pm 13.11 ^a	1358.23 \pm 35.23 ^a	20.67 \pm 3.25 ^a	120.55 \pm 20.11 ^a	2.3 \pm 0.21 ^b
$\Delta\text{FgLetm2}$	1300.02 \pm 24.53 ^a	1250.22 \pm 48.37 ^a	19.66 \pm 1.67 ^b	122.63 \pm 15.37 ^a	2.43 \pm 0.20 ^b
$\Delta\text{FgLetm2-C}$	1360.56 \pm 15.21 ^a	1400.26 \pm 68.70 ^a	21.79 \pm 3.22 ^a	120.33 \pm 18.54 ^a	2.1 \pm 0.25 ^b
$\Delta\text{FgLetm12}$	953.56 \pm 30.14 ^b	875.65 \pm 50.32 ^b	2.34 \pm 0.86 ^b	2.56 \pm 0.25 ^b	4.17 \pm 0.14 ^a

*Values followed by the same letter are not significantly different at $P = 0.05$ for each treatment.

1 **Table 3 Deoxynivalenol productions of the wild type, mutants and**
 2 **complemented strains in TBI, wheat kernel medium and infected**
 3 **spikelets**

	TBI	Wheat kernel	Infected spikelet
Strain	DON production ($\mu\text{g/g}$ dried mycelia)	DON production ($\mu\text{g/mg}$ ergosterol)	DON production (mg/mg ergosterol)
PH-1	650.75 \pm 7.07 ^{a*}	398.88 \pm 13.07 ^a	581.53 \pm 30.28 ^a
$\Delta\text{FgLetm1}$	38.24 \pm 2.81 ^b	11.81 \pm 1.40 ^b	228.61 \pm 20.25 ^b
$\Delta\text{FgLetm1-C}$	630.80 \pm 12.86 ^a	428.56 \pm 14.59 ^a	536.27 \pm 17.36 ^a
$\Delta\text{FgLetm2}$	635.07 \pm 13.80 ^a	420.97 \pm 15.58 ^a	566.54 \pm 30.85 ^a
$\Delta\text{FgLetm2-C}$	660.46 \pm 8.96 ^a	394.22 \pm 15.08 ^a	605.03 \pm 35.18 ^a
$\Delta\text{FgLetm12}$	35.93 \pm 3.53 ^b	9.43 \pm 2.89 ^b	188.10 \pm 19.51 ^b

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 5 *Values followed by the same letter are not significantly different at $P = 0.05$ for each
 6 treatment.

Proof